

Research Article

Evaporation and the difference between precipitation and evaporation in Bulgaria

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Abstract

This study examines the total evaporation and precipitation-evaporation difference in Bulgaria. Data from ERA5-Land reanalysis for the period 1979–2023 were processed using statistical methods. The results show that the main factors for evaporation in Bulgaria are air temperature and precipitation. Evaporation has a positive trend due to the rise in air temperature. This trend is significant only in mountainous regions, which are well-supplied with water. Evaporation is somewhat limited in the other parts of the country because of the water deficits in the warm part of the year. Precipitation is a possible source of water for the earth's surface, but there has been only an insignificant increase in it in recent decades. Precipitation-evaporation difference remains relatively unchanged during the studied period, which is a favorable trend, as there is no increase in the water deficit in Bulgaria on an annual basis. In addition, most of the country has positive values in terms of the average annual values of precipitation-evaporation difference. However, there is a need to introduce monitoring of actual evaporation, because this study has shown that different calculation methods give different results, which is a significant problem in determining how much precipitation remains in a given area. The exact values of this indicator are extremely important for various sectors of the economy such as agriculture, water supply and sewage, transport, energy, etc.

Key words: Atmosphere-surface interaction, climate change, trends, water balance, water cycle

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1. Introduction

Evaporation is one of the important elements of climate. It shows how much of the water on the earth's (or water's) surface enters the atmosphere. Evaporation depends both on the availability of water for evaporation and the temperature of the ground (water) surface and the air. The greater the temperature difference is, the greater the evaporation is and vice versa. Evaporation also depends on the saturation of the air with water vapor. Higher saturation (relative humidity closer to 100%) leads to less evaporation and vice versa. It should be pointed out that evaporation occurs only when the air temperature is higher than the surface temperature. When the temperature of the surface is higher than that of the air, a condensation process of water vapor is observed. Evaporation is an important element of the water balance of a given territory

or water area. The difference between precipitation and evaporation indicates water inflow (or outflow in case evaporation is greater than precipitation) to a given territory or water area in terms of the atmospheric element of the water balance. In the present study, the term total evaporation is used as defined in the ERA5-Land reanalysis of the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) 2022). This is actually the measured evapotranspiration according to the terminology more commonly used in scientific literature since the total evaporation in ERA5-Land reanalysis comprises evaporation from bare soil, evaporation from water surfaces (excluding the ocean), evaporation from the top of canopy and evaporation through the transpiration of plants.

Studies on the total evaporation in Bulgaria are few. This is mainly due to the fact that there were no direct measurements of evaporation in the past. It has been calculated using various indirect methods. The first such study, which covers almost the entire territory of Bulgaria, was conducted by Zypkov (1967). He has used the water balance method to calculate evaporation in the country's river basins. He also compared this method with some other methods for calculation of evaporation. Vasileva (2016) has calculated the actual evapotranspiration in the Lefedzha river basin for the period 2000–2013 using modeling with empirical formulas. Vasileva and Orehova (2015) have estimated the potential and actual evapotranspiration in the Danube plain region using empirical equations. Vasileva (2023) has calculated the actual evapotranspiration in the Tundzha river basin. Nojarov (2020) has shown the intra-annual course and multi-annual trends in evaporation in five karst regions in Bulgaria. The study of Teuling et al. (2019) has revealed some data about evapotranspiration across Europe. Due to the lack of direct measurements of evaporation, many of the studies focus on the potential evapotranspiration in Bulgaria, which is calculated using various empirical formulas that are based on climate elements often measured at weather stations, such as air temperature and precipitation. It should be noted that potential evapotranspiration is the maximum possible evapotranspiration under given atmospheric conditions and differs from actual evapotranspiration. Such studies are those of Tzenkova et al. (2008) for the Bulgarian Danube coast, Anwar et al. (2023) for entire Bulgaria, Kazandjiev et al. (2022) for entire Bulgaria, Gerginov and Antonov (2019) for the loess in northeastern Bulgaria, Georgieva et al. (2022) for entire Bulgaria, Nistor et al. (2017) for southeastern Europe. In recent decades, the development of remote sensing methods has made it possible to measure actual evapotranspiration. Satellite data are used to determine the actual evapotranspiration in Bulgaria. This is done in the studies of Cazanescu and Pienaru (2014), Vasileva et al. (2018), Stoyanova et al. (2023), Kamenova et al. (2023).

The aim of the study is to reveal the spatial distribution and temporal dynamics of the actual evaporation in Bulgaria. Another goal of the study is to calculate the difference between precipitation and evaporation, thus obtaining the water that accumulates (or the opposite) in a given territory or water area. This indicator is more important than precipitation, as it shows more precisely the presence or absence of system destabilizing processes such as drought or waterlogging. In turn, this climatic aspect is crucial for various economic sectors such as agriculture, transport, energy production from renewable sources, etc.

2. Data and methods

This study uses monthly data from the ERA5-Land reanalysis of the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) 2022). The research period is 1979–2023. The spatial resolution of the data is 0.1x0.1°. The climatic elements that were extracted from the above-mentioned database are air temperature (2 m above the earth's surface), precipitation and evaporation. It should be kept in mind that evaporation in the reanalysis is represented as a heat flux carried by water vapor that is directed from the land (water) surface upwards to the atmosphere. Such fluxes are denoted by a minus sign. During condensation, the heat flux carried by the water vapor is directed downward towards the earth's (water's) surface and it is denoted by a plus sign. Comparison between the annual precipitation sums from ERA5-Land reanalysis and measurements at different meteorological stations in Bulgaria has shown an overestimation of about 100 mm of the reanalysis data. However, there are no direct measurements of total evaporation in Bulgaria and therefore it cannot be compared with the data from ERA5-Land reanalysis. For this reason, the study uses precipitation and evaporation data from ERA5-Land reanalysis, since the potential deviations should be similar in both climatic elements. To conduct a more detailed examination of the temporal dynamics of evaporation and precipitation-evaporation difference, three grid cells were selected, which represent different types of climate in Bulgaria. The first one has coordinates of its center 43.5°N, 25°E, it is located near the city of Pleven and it represents the common for Bulgaria lowlands type of climate. The second one has coordinates of its center 43.3°N, 28°E, it is located near the city of Varna and it represents a seaside type of climate. The third one has coordinates of its center 42.1°N, 23.5°E, it is located in the area of Musala peak and it represents a mountain type of climate.

Climate data are processed using statistical methods (Wilks 2006). The level of statistical significance for all calculations is $p \leq 0.05$. The trend analysis was done by means of linear regression. The linear regression represents the relationship between the independent variable (time) and the dependent variable (e.g. precipitation, evaporation) through a linear equation based on the observed values. The equation is:

$$Y = a + bX \quad (1)$$

where:

X is the explanatory variable, Y is the dependent variable, a is the intercept and b is the slope.

Spearman's rank nonparametric correlation was used to reveal the relationships of evaporation with precipitation and air temperature. Its advantage is that it is not affected by the statistical distribution of the studied elements. It is calculated according to the following equation:

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)} \quad (2)$$

where:

r_s is Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, d_i is the difference between the two ranks of each observation, and n is the number of observations.

The residuals (calculated based on linear regression for each month of the year and for the annual average values) of the relevant variables were used for the calculation of correlation coefficients. The residuals are free of any trend,

which is an important condition for the correct determination of the relationships between the various climatic elements. After that, the results of the correlation can be a good basis to draw conclusions on whether trends in one element are connected with trends in another element.

3. Results

The average annual evaporation in Bulgaria for the period 1991–2020 is shown in Fig. 1. The highest values of evaporation are observed along the Black Sea coast and especially in its southern part. This is due to the constant source of water such as the Black Sea and relatively high air temperatures throughout the year. Areas of the country that have relatively lower altitudes (higher air temperature) and do not have large bodies of water, such as the region in northwestern Bulgaria that is far from the Danube river, parts of central western Bulgaria and northeastern Bulgaria, are characterized by the lowest evaporation.

The intra-annual course of evaporation in Bulgaria for the period 1991–2020 in the three studied grid cells is shown in Fig. 2. In all three regions, the course is similar with a maximum in June and a minimum in January. The main cause for such a distribution is the course of the air temperature, which is the lowest in January and, accordingly, this leads to the lowest evaporation. In June, the air temperature is high, but not the highest. One typical for Bulgaria feature of this month is the maximum precipitation, which ensures a high water content on the earth's surface. This, in turn, determines the maximum values of evaporation. A

Figure 1. Average annual evaporation (mm) in Bulgaria for the period 1991–2020.

slower increase in evaporation in the region of Musala peak is observed in March and April, which is due to the shift of the minimum air temperature to February and the fact that March and April are still winter months in the high mountain.

The following two figures were included in connection with the intra-annual course shown in Fig. 2, and due to the fact that the highest air temperatures in

Figure 2. The intra-annual course of evaporation (mm) in the three studied grid cells—Pleven (lowlands climate type), Varna (seaside climate type) and Musala peak (mountain climate type) for the period 1991–2020.

Figure 3. Average evaporation (mm) in Bulgaria in January for the period 1991–2020.

Bulgaria are currently (2000–2020) observed in August (Nojarov 2023), which is also the driest month. Fig. 3 shows the average evaporation for the period 1991–2020 in January, and Fig. 4—in August. In January (Fig. 3), evaporation values are low, between 0 and -0.4 mm over most of the country. This is due to the low air temperatures then. Evaporation values increase in the east-south-east direction and they are highest along the southern Black Sea coast. Air temperatures are high there, which is largely due to the higher temperature of sea water. The very presence of a large water basin is also a prerequisite for higher evaporation, as it is a constant source of water and, accordingly, of water vapor.

The spatial distribution of evaporation in August for the period 1991–2020 in Bulgaria is shown in Fig. 4. The values are much higher than those in January, and a large territorial differentiation is also observed. It should be pointed out that in this month the main factor is the presence of water in the earth's surface, and not so much air temperature. The highest values of evaporation are observed in all high mountainous parts of Bulgaria—Stara Planina, the Rilo-Rhodope massif, and the rest of the mountains in southwestern Bulgaria. Water reserves in the earth's surface are still high in these regions in August, and the combination with higher air temperatures results in high evaporation values. The Danube river basin also has high evaporation, which is due to the river itself providing enough water for evaporation. High values are also observed along the Black Sea coast, where there is a constant source of water and water vapor, such as the Black Sea. The lowest evaporation occurs in low-

Figure 4. Average evaporation (mm) in Bulgaria in August for the period 1991–2020.

land areas of Bulgaria where there are no large water sources and accordingly the water content on the earth's surface in August is minimal. For this reason, despite the very high air temperatures in this month, there is little evaporation.

Table 1 shows correlation coefficients between evaporation and air temperature in the three studied regions for the period 1979–2023. There is one interesting tendency of reversing the sign of the relationship from winter to summer. During cold months, the correlation is negative, and in many of the months, it is also statistically significant. This means that higher temperatures are associated with higher evaporation and vice versa. During summer months, the relationship is the opposite—higher air temperature is associated with lower evaporation and vice versa, and in some of the months the correlation is statistically significant. During the cold half of the year in Bulgaria, the earth's surface has sufficient reserves of water. Due to this fact, any increase in air temperature leads to an increase in evaporation. In summer, the water content of the earth's surface is low. Higher temperatures lead to even less water content and therefore less evaporation, due to the fact that there is simply nothing to evaporate. There are some differences in the temporal manifestation of the above-mentioned dependencies in the different studied grid cells. In the area around Pleven, this reversal of the relationship from winter to summer is the most robust with statistically significant values in both winter and summer. In Varna, the statistically significant negative values are at the beginning of spring, because then the temperature of the seawater is lowest and the contrast between air and water temperatures is greatest. Accordingly, the evaporation is most strongly dependent on air temperature during this period. The positive correlation values are also shifted towards the end of the summer and autumn, which is due to the slower cooling of the water and correspondingly the smaller difference between water and air temperatures then. In the region of Musala

Table 1. Spearman's correlation between evaporation (mm) and air temperature (°C) in grid cells Pleven (lowlands climate type), Varna (seaside climate type) and Musala peak (mountain climate type) for the period 1979–2023. Statistically significant numbers are shown in bold.

	Pleven	Varna	Musala
January	-0.89	0.14	-0.72
February	-0.85	-0.06	-0.67
March	-0.85	-0.51	-0.69
April	-0.55	-0.51	-0.55
May	-0.20	-0.24	-0.36
June	-0.12	-0.10	-0.66
July	0.59	0.19	-0.05
August	0.68	0.42	0.02
September	0.31	0.50	-0.16
October	0.28	0.38	-0.49
November	-0.26	0.37	-0.70
December	-0.60	0.03	-0.32
Annual	0.37	0.25	-0.55

peak, there is no complete drying of the earth's surface (there are also some permanent lakes), and therefore, higher air temperature leads to higher evaporation during most of the year. This is confirmed also by the average annual values. In the lowlands type of climate (Pleven), the inverse proportional relationship between evaporation and air temperature prevails, which is confirmed by the statistically significant coefficient of the average annual values.

Table 2 shows the correlations between evaporation and precipitation in the three studied grid cells for the period 1979–2023. There is, too, a reversal in the sign of the correlation between winter and summer. In summer and early autumn (grid cells Pleven and Varna) and at the beginning of winter (grid cell Varna) the correlation is negative. This means that more precipitation is associated with less evaporation and vice versa. During this part of the year, usually rainy periods are characterized by lower air temperatures, which reduces evaporation. During the winter months (mostly in grid cell Musala), the correlation is positive. During this season in Bulgaria, precipitation is most often associated with higher air temperatures, which explains the statistically significant values in Table 2. The average annual values in the low altitude grid cells show a negative and statistically significant correlation, which means that, in general, higher precipitation is associated with less evaporation and vice versa.

Table 2. Spearman's correlation between evaporation (mm) and precipitation (mm) in grid cells Pleven (lowlands climate type), Varna (seaside climate type) and Musala peak (mountain climate type) for the period 1979–2023. Statistically significant numbers are shown in bold.

	Pleven	Varna	Musala
January	0.22	-0.18	0.36
February	0.36	0.05	0.35
March	0.26	-0.19	0.36
April	0.21	0.07	0.15
May	0.20	-0.13	-0.05
June	0.01	-0.33	0.27
July	-0.76	-0.66	-0.47
August	-0.51	-0.63	-0.38
September	-0.45	-0.53	-0.33
October	-0.58	-0.75	-0.12
November	-0.35	-0.48	0.00
December	0.01	-0.34	0.03
Annual	-0.83	-0.76	-0.08

Table 3 shows the trends in evaporation in the corresponding grid cells representing the three climate types for the period 1979–2023 according to data from ERA5-Land reanalysis, European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). In Pleven, there are statistically significant positive evaporation trends in February, March and April. This is due to rising air temperatures (the negative correlation in Table 1) and still good water reserves on the earth's surface during this time of year. A significant negative trend in evaporation is

observed only in September. This is due to the insignificant increase in temperatures and low (or almost non-existent) water reserves on the earth's surface during this month, which follows the month with the least precipitation, when evaporation also decreases. The increase in precipitation in this month (Nojarov 2017a) also contributes to the decrease in evaporation according to Table 2. In Varna, there is a statistically significant increase in evaporation in March. This is due to the greater amounts of water contained in the earth's surface and rising air temperatures (the negative correlation in Table 1). At Musala peak, there is a significant increase in evaporation both in the annual average values and in the months from May to July and November and December. The causes for these trends are the relatively good reserves of water in the mountainous areas throughout the year, including summer. On the other hand, there is also a significant increase in air temperature in these regions of Bulgaria.

Table 3. Evaporation trends (in mm) in grid cells Pleven (lowlands climate type), Varna (seaside climate type) and Musala peak (mountain climate type) for the period 1979–2023. Statistically significant numbers are shown in bold.

	Pleven	Varna	Musala
January	-0.0023	-0.0011	-0.0013
February	-0.0066	-0.0020	-0.0014
March	-0.0068	-0.0103	-0.0024
April	-0.0071	-0.0038	-0.0046
May	-0.0030	-0.0042	-0.0195
June	-0.0018	-0.0052	-0.0047
July	0.0048	-0.0008	-0.0064
August	0.0130	0.0038	-0.0046
September	0.0184	0.0024	0.0026
October	0.0026	0.0040	0.0003
November	-0.0006	-0.0002	-0.0050
December	-0.0004	-0.0004	-0.0015
Annual	0.0009	-0.0015	-0.0040

An important element for the water balance of the country is how much precipitation remains on the earth's surface. This can be represented as the difference between precipitation and evaporation. The available data from ERA5-Land reanalysis allow the corresponding calculations to be made. Fig. 5 shows the spatial distribution of the average annual values of precipitation-evaporation difference in Bulgaria for the period 1991–2020. The figure shows that the largest water surplus (over 1.2 mm) is observed in the high mountains of Bulgaria—Stara Planina, Rila, Pirin and Western Rhodopes. This is due to higher precipitation and lower air temperatures, which cause less evaporation. Accordingly, these are also the main „water source“ areas in the country that give start to many of the rivers, as this excess water has to be removed through certain routes from the respective area. The parts of Bulgaria that have a water deficit within the year are generally two—the Danube River and the Black Sea

coast. This is due to two main factors. The first is the year-round availability of water, provided by either the Danube River or the Black Sea. This allows for virtually unlimited evaporation. The second factor is the low altitude of these territories, which causes high average annual air temperatures. They, in turn, also contribute to increased evaporation. The relatively low annual precipitation amounts in the majority of these two regions should also be taken into account here (the only exception is the southern Black Sea coast). In general, the majority of the territory of Bulgaria has a water surplus for the studied period in terms of precipitation-evaporation difference.

Figure 5. Average annual values of precipitation-evaporation difference (mm) in Bulgaria for the period 1991–2020.

The intra-annual course of precipitation-evaporation difference in the three studied grid cells for the period 1991–2020 is shown in Fig. 6. In the low part of the country (Pleven and Varna grid cells), the maximum (positive values, water surplus) in the intra-annual course is in the months of December and January, and the minimum (negative values, water deficit) is in June–July. It should be pointed out that the maximum in the Pleven grid cell is about 1 mm, while the minimum is about -2 mm, i.e. the water surplus in winter is less than the water deficit in summer. In the high mountain parts (Musala peak) the maximum is in April (positive values, water surplus) and the secondary one is in December (positive values, water surplus), and the minimum is in August (negative values, water deficit). The maximum in April could be explained by the maximum of precipitation, which at Musala peak is in April (Nojarov 2012). Also, in this

month, the air temperature in the high mountain is still low, which causes lower evaporation. In the lower parts of Bulgaria, the period with positive values of precipitation-evaporation difference is from October to March, and negative values are typical for the period from April to September. Thus, half of the year has water surplus and the other half has water deficit. In the area of Musala peak, the period with water surplus is from September to June, and the period with water deficit is in the remaining two months—July and August.

Figure 6. The intra-annual course of precipitation-evaporation difference (mm) in the three studied grid cells—Pleven (lowlands climate type), Varna (seaside climate type) and Musala peak (mountain climate type) for the period 1991–2020.

In connection with the intra-annual course, the next two figures show the spatial distribution of precipitation-evaporation difference for the period 1991–2020 in Bulgaria in two opposite (in terms of water deficit/surplus) months—January (Fig. 7) and August (Fig. 8). Fig. 7 shows that in January, the precipitation-evaporation difference has positive values, i.e. there is excess water everywhere. This surplus is the largest (over 2 mm) in the southern mountainous parts of Bulgaria—Pirin, Rhodopes and Strandzha. This is due to the greater precipitation there, because of the Mediterranean cyclones, which during this part of the year pass in most cases south of Bulgaria. Also, these parts have a higher altitude, and correspondingly, the air temperature is lower, which reduces evaporation and leads to a larger water surplus. In the northern parts of the country, the precipitation-evaporation difference is the smallest due to lower precipitation and higher air temperatures because of the low altitude of these areas.

Fig. 8 shows that all of Bulgaria has negative values of precipitation-evaporation difference in August. This is generally due to the low precipitation and high air temperatures, which cause a lot of evaporation. The lowest values (greatest water deficit) are observed along the course of the Danube River, the Black Sea coast and the Eastern Rhodopes. The causes for these low values in the first two regions have already been explained above in the section dealing with the average annual values, the presence of a permanent water source that allows

Figure 7. Spatial distribution of precipitation-evaporation difference (mm) in Bulgaria in January for the period 1991–2020.

Figure 8. Spatial distribution of precipitation-evaporation difference (mm) in Bulgaria in August for the period 1991–2020.

unlimited evaporation and low altitude that leads to high air temperatures. In the Eastern Rhodopes in August, air temperatures are very high, and there are several water reservoirs (large dams) along the Arda River, which are sources of water for evaporation.

Table 4 shows the trends in precipitation-evaporation difference in the three studied grid cells in Bulgaria for the period 1979–2023 according to data from ERA5-Land reanalysis. In Pleven, a statistically significant increase in this element is observed only in October. This is mostly due to the statistically significant increase in precipitation, air temperature and evaporation showing no significant change. Considering the significant water deficit at the beginning of this month, this trend can be defined as favorable. During the remaining months of the year, the trends have different signs and are not statistically significant. Average annual values are decreasing, but not significantly. In Varna in October, there is a statistically significant increase in precipitation-evaporation difference, the causes being the same as in Pleven. Here again, this trend could be defined as favorable for water resources. There is a statistically significant negative trend in April. It is mainly due to the increase in evaporation and to a lesser extent to the insignificant decrease in precipitation. Evaporation rises due to rising air temperature. This trend is unfavorable, since the period of the year with water deficit, according to this indicator, begins in April, and this will lead to an increase in the water deficit during the warm half of the year. Average annual values in this grid cell do not show any significant trend. At Musala peak, there is one month with a significant decrease in precipitation-evaporation difference, May. The cause for this is the significant increase in evaporation (Table 3) and the insignificant decrease in precipitation. The increased evaporation is due to the significant increase in air temperature during this month. The observed trend is unfavorable since the reduced water reserves of the mountain in May determine lower water reserves in the mountain and surrounding terri-

Table 4. Trends in precipitation-evaporation difference (mm) in grid cells Pleven (lowlands climate type), Varna (seaside climate type) and Musala peak (mountain climate type) for the period 1979–2023. Statistically significant numbers are shown in bold.

	Pleven	Varna	Musala
January	0.0053	0.0158	0.0227
February	-0.0031	-0.0011	0.0018
March	-0.0021	-0.0085	0.0184
April	-0.0138	-0.0163	-0.0026
May	-0.0203	-0.0008	-0.0348
June	0.0029	0.0012	0.0243
July	-0.0114	-0.0147	-0.0234
August	-0.0191	-0.0164	-0.0171
September	0.0222	0.0003	0.0143
October	0.0219	0.0226	0.0131
November	-0.0059	-0.0097	-0.0190
December	-0.0032	0.0081	0.0008
Annual	-0.0022	-0.0016	-0.0001

tories throughout the summer season. There are no significant changes in the average annual values. In conclusion, it can be pointed out that despite the rising air temperatures in Bulgaria in the last few decades, there has been no significant decrease in precipitation-evaporation difference, which means that, from a climatic point of view, the water balance is still stable.

4. Discussion

As mentioned above, there are two main approaches to calculate evaporation from a given area. The first is through the water balance method, where evaporation is equal to the difference between precipitation and river runoff (Zyapkov 1967). In the second approach, evaporation is calculated as the sum of evaporation from bare soil, from inland water bodies, from the top of the canopy, and from plant transpiration. Current methods use different information and modeling to directly calculate these four components of evaporation. Evaporation cannot be measured directly by remote sensing, so other data are used, such as downward shortwave radiation, downward longwave radiation, albedo, air temperature, air humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, soil temperature, etc. (Arboleda et al. 2018). Land cover data is used to precisely define its type—bare soil, water body or vegetation. The remote sensing inputs are then processed through various models to obtain the actual evaporation in a given area. In the specific case, the ERA5 reanalysis uses the models Surface Schemes for Exchange Processes over Land (TESSEL) (Viterbo and Beljaars 1995) and H-TESEL (Balsamo et al. 2009).

The study of Zyapkov (1967), which covers the entire territory of Bulgaria, reveals that average annual values of evaporation are in the range from 1 to 1.5 mm. These values are lower than those shown in Fig. 1, which can be explained by two possible causes. The first one is the method of calculation, which in the study of Zyapkov is indirect, i.e. there are no direct measurements. The second cause is the rise in air temperature, which has also led to an increase in evaporation. In addition, the author reveals a tendency of decreasing evaporation with increasing altitude in all mountains in Bulgaria, which is not exactly the case using current data (Fig. 1). Some mountain parts (Stara Planina) have high evaporation values. Vasileva (2016) has made calculations of total evaporation in the Lefedzha river basin (central northern Bulgaria) for the period 2000–2013 using two models (methods). According to the first model, the average annual evaporation values are in the range of 1.4–1.6 mm. According to the second model, the values are in the range of 1.3–1.5 mm. These values are again lower than the ERA5-Land reanalysis data, which are about 1.8 mm. The differences may again be due to the approach of calculating the total evaporation rather than directly measuring it. Vasileva (2023), using an indirect method, has obtained average annual values of actual total evaporation in the Tundzha River basin (southern Bulgaria) in the range from 0.8 to 1.6 mm. These values are again lower than those presented in Fig. 1. In both studies of Vasileva (2016, 2023), no dependence between altitude and evaporation was observed, as in the article of Zyapkov (1967). Orehova and Gerginov (2022) have used *AquiMod* software to calculate actual evapotranspiration, based on other climatic data such as air temperature, precipitation, and potential evapotranspiration. Their results for meteorological stations Pleven and Kazanlak

show annual mean actual evapotranspiration values of about 1.3 mm, which is again lower compared to the results shown in Fig. 1. Vasileva et al. (2018) have used satellite data to establish the total evaporation in Bulgaria for the period 2000–2014. The spatial distribution is quite similar to that in Fig. 1 with the highest values in the Stara Planina region and the southern Black Sea coast. Annual average evaporation values are in the range from 0.8 to 2.7 mm, and they are similar to those of the ERA5-Land reanalysis. Also, a trend of increasing evaporation was revealed in the period 2000–2014, which, however, is not significant. This coincides with the data in Table 3, where no significant trend in evaporation is observed in the lower parts of Bulgaria. Stoyanova et al. (2023) have used satellite data for evaporation in Bulgaria for the period 2011–2021 during the warm half of the year (May–October). The values for various points in northern and southern Bulgaria range from 1 to 4 mm, slightly lower in southern Bulgaria. These values are similar to the August values presented in Fig. 4. Teuling et al. (2019) have used indirect methods to calculate the total evaporation in Europe for the period 1960–2010. Their results show that the average annual evaporation in Bulgaria is in the range of 1.1 to 1.6 mm. The analysis of the previous studies on the subject shows an interesting dependence. Calculation of total evaporation by indirect methods, which are based on available data for certain climatic elements such as air temperature and precipitation or the use of the water balance of a certain territory, results in obtaining lower values of evaporation. A similar conclusion about the entire catchment area of the Danube river has been made by Pekárová et al. (2023). On the other hand, the use of evaporation measurements by satellites shows higher evaporation values in Bulgaria.

Publications on the difference between precipitation and evaporation are almost absent, so it is difficult to compare the results of this study. Lucarini et al. (2007) have assessed data from various reanalyses for the Danube River basin for the period 1961–1990. This assessment includes both precipitation and evaporation, as well as their difference. The intra-annual course of evaporation is similar to that in Fig. 2 with a minimum of just over 0 mm in December–January and a maximum of 2.7 to 4 mm in June. The precipitation–evaporation difference has a minimum in July and a maximum in November in most of the reanalyses. The minimum values in July are negative and range from -0.3 to -1.3 mm. The maximum values are positive from 1.5 to 2.2 mm. This intra-annual course shows generally higher values than those in Fig. 6, but it should be taken into account that the Danube River basin covers more northern territories compared to Bulgaria, where precipitation is more and air temperatures are lower. In this sense, the obtained in this study precipitation–evaporation difference is comparable to that of Lucarini et al. (2007). Thus, it can be assumed that despite the mentioned above discrepancies in evaporation data and the overestimation of precipitation in ERA5-Land reanalysis, the obtained result for precipitation–evaporation difference is sufficiently reliable.

The results obtained in the present study show that certain measures would be necessary in water usage. The values in Table 4 reveal a decrease in atmospheric water inflow in summer and an increase in autumn. The decreasing trend in summer is not particularly favorable for water management, as this is when water consumption in agriculture and households is greatest. The increase in autumn cannot compensate for this deficit. Thus, the construction

of new dams and proper management and maintenance of the already built ones should become a priority policy of the country to deal with the expected climate changes. The observed trends in precipitation and evaporation will have a negative impact on other areas as well, such as transport, electricity production, food industry, etc. There will be certain consequences for ecosystems and biodiversity, as some species will have to be replaced by others that are better adapted to changing climatic conditions. This can happen both naturally and through human intervention. In agriculture, crops that are more adapted to unevenly distributed rainfall during the warm half-year should be grown. Future research on the topic should focus on the better agreement between reanalysis data and ground-based measurements. Improving the quality of source information will provide a better basis for accurate and timely planning of the necessary measures to deal with climate change.

5. Conclusion

This research shows that the main climatic factors for evaporation in Bulgaria are air temperature and precipitation. In recent decades, the evaporation has increased due to the rise in air temperature. However, the increase is not as significant as that of the temperature. The causes for this are the limited reserves of water on the earth's surface in the low parts of the country, which do not allow a significant increase in evaporation. On the other hand, in mountainous regions, which are well supplied with water, evaporation increases significantly and synchronously with the increase in air temperature. Precipitation is a possible source of water for the earth's surface, but there has been no significant increase in it in recent decades over the Balkan Peninsula (Nojarov 2017b; Popov and Svetozarevich 2021), which limits evaporation. In this regard, the precipitation-evaporation difference remains relatively unchanged during the studied period. In conditions of globally rising temperatures and scenarios in which Bulgaria turns into a desert, this is a favorable trend, as there is no increase in the water deficit in different parts of the country. Most of Bulgaria has positive values in terms of the average annual precipitation-evaporation difference. In the future, there is a need to introduce monitoring of actual evaporation, because different calculation methods give different results, which is a significant problem in determining how much precipitation remains in a given area. The exact values of this indicator are extremely important for various sectors of the economy such as agriculture, water supply and sewage, transport, energy, etc.

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Additional information

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.